

HOW DOES ORGANIZATION BASED SELF-ESTEEM PLAY A ROLE IN AFFECTING MOONLIGHTING INTENTION AND CONTEXTUAL PERFORMANCE IN THE TOURISM ENTERPRISES?

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Abstract

In this research, it is aimed to determine the effect of organization-based self-esteem on moonlighting intention and contextual performance in tourism enterprises and to examine the differentiation of research variables in terms of demographic factors. For this purpose, a questionnaire was applied to 397 employees in tourism enterprises. Analyzes were performed using data obtained from questionnaires. The result of the analysis showed that, employees' moonlighting intention and contextual performance could significantly be explained by organization-based self-esteem. It was determined that a one-unit increase in organization-based self-esteem resulted in a decrease in the moonlighting intention and an increase in the contextual performance. However, it was concluded that there is a very weak negative relationship between organization-based self-esteem and moonlighting intention of employees, and a very high positive relationship between their contextual performances. According to the analyzes, it was determined that there were significant differences between some of the demographic variables of the participants and their organization-based self-esteem, moonlighting intention and contextual performance.

Keywords: Organization-based self-esteem; Moonlighting intention; Contextual performance; Tourism industry.

COMO A AUTOESTIMA BASEADA NA ORGANIZAÇÃO DESEMPENHA NA INTENÇÃO DE LUAR E NO DESEMPENHO CONTEXTUAL NAS EMPRESAS TURÍSTICAS?

Resumo

Nesta pesquisa, pretende-se determinar o efeito da auto-estima baseada na organização na intenção de trabalho clandestino e no desempenho contextual em empreendimentos turísticos e examinar a diferenciação das variáveis de pesquisa em termos de fatores demográficos. Para o efeito, foi aplicado um questionário a 397 colaboradores de empreendimentos turísticos. As análises foram realizadas por meio de dados obtidos a partir de questionários. O resultado da análise mostrou que a intenção de trabalho clandestino e o desempenho contextual dos funcionários podem ser explicados significativamente pela autoestima baseada na organização. Foi determinado que um aumento de uma unidade na auto-estima baseada na organização resultou em uma diminuição na intenção de fazer bico e um aumento no desempenho contextual. No entanto, concluiu-se que existe uma relação negativa muito fraca entre a autoestima baseada na organização e a intenção de trabalho clandestino dos funcionários, e uma relação positiva muito alta entre seus desempenhos contextuais. De acordo com as análises, foi determinado que havia diferenças significativas entre algumas das variáveis demográficas dos participantes e sua auto-estima baseada na organização, intenção de fazer bico e desempenho contextual.

Palavras-chave: Auto-estima baseada na organização; Intenção de trabalho clandestino; Desempenho contextual; Indústria do turismo.

¿CÓMO LA AUTOESTIMA BASADA EN LA ORGANIZACIÓN JUEGA UN PAPEL EN LA INTENCIÓN DE LUMINOSIDAD Y EL DESEMPEÑO CONTEXTUAL EN LAS EMPRESAS TURÍSTICAS?

Resumen

En esta investigación, se pretende determinar el efecto de la autoestima basada en la organización sobre la intención de trabajar en otro lugar y el desempeño contextual en las empresas turísticas y examinar la diferenciación de las variables de investigación en términos de factores demográficos. Para ello, se aplicó un cuestionario a 397 empleados de empresas turísticas. Los análisis se realizaron utilizando datos obtenidos de cuestionarios. El resultado del análisis mostró que la intención de segundo empleo de los empleados y el desempeño contextual podrían explicarse significativamente por la autoestima basada en la organización. Se determinó que un aumento de una unidad en la autoestima basada en la organización resultó en una disminución en la intención de pluriempleo y un aumento en el desempeño contextual. Sin embargo, se concluyó que existe una relación negativa muy débil entre la autoestima basada en la organización y la intención de pluriempleo de los empleados, y una relación positiva muy alta entre sus desempeños contextuales. De acuerdo con los análisis, se determinó que había diferencias significativas entre algunas de las variables demográficas de los participantes y su autoestima basada en la organización, la intención de pluriempleo y el desempeño contextual.

Palabras clave: Autoestima basada en la organización; Intención de pluriempleo; Desempeño contextual; Industria turística.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the context of service production, it is considered that the main factor of production of tourism enterprises is

human resources. Especially today, due to the rapidity of change, keeping up with these alterations has become dependent on the efficiency and effectiveness of human resources. From this standpoint, the behavior of the

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employees is the most critical factor in boosting productivity and competitiveness of the enterprises and ensuring business continuity. Organizations need qualified, effective and productive employees, and these organizations should make an effort not to lose the qualified staff they employ. In this context, organizational-based self-esteem (OBSE) is of vital importance in terms of the effectiveness and efficiency of the employees in tourism enterprises.

OBSE can boost the performance of employees by making them feel appreciated, important, trusted, respected and more valued for the organization. OBSE will prevent employees from having the intention of moonlighting, which is defined as working in a second job, and will enable them to improve their performance and to act creatively and innovatively in the critical decision-making processes of the organization. In addition, OBSE will reduce the moonlighting intention of employees and can contribute positively to communication, productivity and teamwork, which are pivotal for tourism enterprises.

Consequently, employees will be able to carry out their jobs with as few faults as possible by increasing their performance, to the extent that they are valued in the business they work for, work collaboratively and know that they are important for that business. In addition, they will be able to actively promote the products and services of the enterprise to potential users, do not hesitate to take risks and support the sustainability of the business. Having OBSE will pave the way for employees to pursue innovations and support sustainability, tourist satisfaction and competitive advantage of the enterprise.

In this context, the aim of the study is to reveal whether OBSE has an effect on the moonlighting intention and contextual performance of employees in tourism enterprises. For this purpose, basically, the conceptual framework of OBSE, moonlighting intention and contextual performance will be discussed within the scope of the research. Finally, the study will be concluded with the methodological structure and evaluations of the results obtained from the findings within the research.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Organization-Based Self-Esteem

Self-esteem is a comprehensive evaluation of one's self. Self-esteem is closely related to the individual's attitudes and behaviors, and therefore to their performance. The performance of individuals will affect the degree to which the organization's goals are achieved. Therefore, when evaluated in terms of organizational efficiency, self-esteem becomes an important variable, since the individuals with high self-esteem tend to develop and maintain positive attitudes and behaviors. These individuals know that their existence serves organizational purposes and is effective in meeting needs. Therefore, these people feel higher job satisfaction and become more productive within the organization (Yüner, 2018).

Pierce et al. (1989) introduced the concept of organization-based self-esteem to develop the concept of self-esteem. Organization-based self-esteem (OBSE) is the degree to which organizational members believe they can

meet their needs by participating in roles in an organizational context. In other words, OBSE reflects the perceived self-worth of individuals operating in the organization. Accordingly, employees with a high level of OBSE are expected to perceive themselves as respected, valuable, effective and meaningful within their organizations (Pierce et al., 1989). At the same time, organizational members with organizational self-esteem believe that they make a difference in every sense in the organization and that they are an important part of the organization they work for (Pierce & Gardner, 2004).

Employees with high OBSE feel important and valuable for the organization to the extent that they believe that they fulfill the duties assigned to them within the organization. On the contrary, employees with low OBSE consider themselves as inadequate and worthless for organizations (Pierce et al., 1989). In addition, Pierce, Gardner and Crowley (2016) stated that individuals with high OBSE experience less depression and feel more life satisfaction and happiness.

Employees who feel valued, know that they are trusted. They try not to lose the trust of their managers and colleagues. When they feel that they are important to the organization, they believe they can make the changes that will make the organization successful. In this case, the organizational bond of these employees will strengthen in favor of the organization. OBSE is closely related to job satisfaction, organizational commitment, motivation, organizational citizenship behavior, job performance and intention to leave, and other attitudes and behaviors related to the organization (Pierce & Gardner, 2004).

A number of studies on OBSE revealed that, OBSE positively affects affective organizational commitment (Güney et al., 2007; Panaccio & Vandenberghe, 2011; Yüner, 2018), job performance (Liu et al., 2013; Çakmak Otluoğlu, 2015; Acaray, 2019; Yıldırım et al., 2019), organizational citizenship behavior (Sekiguchi et al., 2008), occupational well-being (Sun et al., 2021), perceived organizational support (Chan et al. 2013), subjective well-being and organizational climate (Akgemci et al., 2020), job autonomy (Naus et al., 2007), life satisfaction (Akyüz, 2018) and the perception of personal-professional competence (Yıldırım et al., 2019); and, negatively affects procrastination (Kaplan & Keriman, 2019), burnout (Türkmenoğlu, 2020), and organizational cynicism (Naus et al., 2007).

2.2 Moonlighting Intention

Employees often work in one or two jobs outside of their primary job to supplement their household income. This situation is called as moonlighting, which is defined as working in another job, along with the current job (Md Sabron & Abu Hassim, 2018). In other words, moonlighting occurs when the employee does a second job outside of his/her regular working hours. A large number of members of the workforce contribute to the secondary labor market by working additional hours with subsidiary occupations or by starting their own business.

In addition, it is a common practice to work in a second job outside of the primary occupation in both developed and developing countries (Ara & Akbar, 2016). However,

moonlighting also reflects the growing need for flexibility to combine primary work and other jobs to meet family and personal needs, in the face of increasing financial stress due to declining earnings (Arogundade, 2020).

Moonlighting is the second or even third job of a person who works independently for a company due to insufficient income and for reasons such as gaining experience or new skills (e.g. a front office staff working as a guide) (Akoğlan Kozak, 2016). At this point, this approach cannot be prevented because the employees see these activities as a guarantee in case their main job is destroyed (Aytaç, 1997). In the meantime, the short time work has a wider impact on life outside of work, which frequently interacts with job stability and status, in addition to having varied effects on the psychological work environment and working conditions at the site of employment (Rydell & Storman, 2022).

Evidently, such problems can be minimized in companies that provide benefits for their employees and attach importance to occupational safety (Kılıç, 2013). Since the moonlighting occurs when the energy that the employee needs to use in the main job is used in other work or jobs, some organizations threaten to fire such employees. This scenery is not accepted by the supervisors with the claim that it leads to low performance, late arrival, early departure or absenteeism, and decrease in job loyalty in individuals.

Thus, the career advancement of those working in two jobs is hindered (Aytaç, 1997). However, moonlighting, which can also occur when a second job is undertaken without notifying the current employer, can make a noticeable difference in workers' income and ultimately in their standard of living. So, this situation arises as a challenge for both employees and businesses (Kaur & Saini, 2020). Some employers, on the other hand, create measures to prevent layoffs by reducing working hours in collaboration with unions (Oborin, 2022).

One of the main reasons why moonlighting is so popular today is that it emerged as a result of the home-office working environment initiated by the pandemic (Bhardwaj, 2022). In the literature, used as an analogous term to the concept of moonlighting; there are also terms such as portfolio career, dual jobholding, protean career and multiple jobholding.

According to Sangwan (2014), moonlighting is categorized under four headings. The first of these is blue moonlighting; which is defined as when an employee is dissatisfied with his/her current job salary, s/he starts looking for a part-time job for supplement income, but his/her efforts are wasted if the employee cannot find a part-time job.

Second one is, quarter moonlighting; which is observed when the employees often take a part-time job with their current job and spend part of their time in the second job to supplement their current salary and meet their basic needs.

Third, half moonlighting; occurs when the employee devotes half of his/her time to the second job to ensure a more comfortable life. The fourth and last one is full moonlighting, which happens when the employee devoting all his/her time to the second job.

Intrinsically, a substantial number of employees in the workforce can be considered as moonlighters. According to U.S. federal bureau of labor statistics, as of February 2023,

there were over 8 million multiple jobholders. Based on the report, approximately 55% of multiple jobholders were with full-time primary job and part-time secondary job (U.S. Bureau of Labour Statistics, 2023). In addition, due to the long and irregular working hours in the tourism sector, the tendency for moonlighting is expected to be low in Türkiye. However, there has always been a need for long-term and qualified employees in Turkey's hospitality industry.

Studies focusing on the moonlighting problem reveal that moonlighting has a significant effect on job satisfaction (Ara & Akbar, 2016), performance (Ologunde et al., 2013; Fattah & Citta, 2020), organizational commitment and, entrepreneurial motivation (Khatri & Khushboo, 2014; Seema & Sachdeva, 2020), risk of burnout (negative) and time spent with family (Kisumano & Wa-Mbaleka 2017), work commitment and productivity (Arogundade, 2020; Akinde et al., 2020), intention to leave (Rispel et al., 2014), and organizational performance (Amde et al., 2018). However, If their employees work in a similar sector and profession, companies may face huge income losses due to the disclosure of trade secrets due to moonlighting. (Bhardwaj, 2022).

2.3 Contextual Performance

Contextual performance comes into existence when the employee volunteers to do task activities that are not formally part of the job, and helps and collaborates with others in the organization to accomplish tasks given (Borman & Motowidlo, 1997). In other words, contextual performance is not directly related to the basic functions of the job, but rather the quality of social relations with subordinates, superiors, colleagues and customers (Kalay, 2016).

In this sense, the activities of employees towards contextual performance become more of an issue, since contextual performance acts as a catalyst for employees' task activities and processes and contributes to organizational effectiveness in organizational, psychological and social environments (Borman & Motowidlo, 1997). While contextual performance is the extra-role behaviors that the employee performs voluntarily, personal factors such as communication skills, motivations, and personality traits are decisive on contextual performance (Motowidlo & Van Scotter, 1994).

Employee behaviors, that indicate contextual performance, are behaviors that fall outside the definition of the roles assigned to the employee in the organization (Yorulmaz, 2018). Thus, contextual performance does not contribute to the technical processes of the organization, but creates a favourable climate by contributing to the organizational, social and psychological environment, required for its technical functions.

It includes activities that promote the viability of social and organizational relationships and support the psychological climate such as helping and cooperating with others, following the organization's rules and procedures personally even in difficult situations, defending and supporting the organization's goals, putting in extra effort when necessary to successfully complete the task, and voluntarily performing off-duty tasks which are not included in the official description of the job (Motowidlo et al., 1997).

Management team both observe the abilities/skills of the employees and their willingness to participate in the activities that should be carried out on behalf of the organization. Employees who can achieve success by persevering in difficult tasks have gained more importance than employees who constantly create problems and cannot show persistence.

Employees who are compatible with group work, open to cooperation and adhere to the rules, in other words, those who demonstrate contextual performance ensure the dynamism of the organization (Aslan & Yıldırım, 2016). There are different ways to reveal or strengthen contextual performance. For instance, transformational leadership attributes in an organization empower employees to support their contextual performance (Zaw & Takahashi, 2022).

Furthermore, a study conducted in the hospitality industry by Bhardwaj & Kalita (2021) inferred that hotel employees' contextual performance is influenced by organizational culture and employee engagement. On the other hand, contextual performance can become a threat in some cases. The sense of performance pressure among hospitality employees may start a chain reaction that lowers engagement (Rescalvo-Martin et al., 2022).

Studies on contextual performance have shown the positive relationship between contextual performance and person-organization fit (Goodman & Svyantek, 1999; Öcel, 2013; Çam et al., 2020), emotional labor (Ünlü & Yürür, 2011; Acaray, 2019; Onay, 2011), work - quality of life (Tokmak, 2021), job satisfaction (Edwards et al., 2008; Bağcı, 2014; Yorulmaz, 2018), positive psychological capital (Acaray, 2019), proactive personality (Demirbilek et al., 2020), organizational support (Shanock & Eisenberger, 2006; Chen et al., 2009; Riggie et al., 2009; Yıldız & Çakı, 2018), organizational identification (Akbaş Tuna, 2020; Akdoğan et al., 2020), organizational culture (Eryılmaz & Altın Gülova, 2019), job satisfaction and affective commitment (Van Scotter, 2000).

Since the human resource is the most critical factor of production in tourism enterprises, the attitudes experienced by the employees can also be reflected in the organization and their way of doing business. OBSE is important in terms of performing these behaviors in favor of the organization.

The main purpose of this research is to determine the effect of organization-based self-esteem on moonlighting intention and contextual performance in tourism enterprises. In addition, it was also aimed to determine what organizational factors might be that cause employees' moonlighting intention and support contextual performance depending on OBSE level they portray. It is also aimed to examine the differentiation of employees' OBSE, moonlighting intention and contextual performance in terms of demographic factors such as gender, marital status, age, working time in the enterprise, income status and working time in the tourism sector.

In this direction, the hypotheses of the research are formalized as follows:

H1: A significant relationship exist between OBSE, moonlighting intention and contextual performance.

H2: OBSE has a significant effect on moonlighting intention.

H3: OBSE has a significant effect on contextual performance.

H4: (a) OBSE, (b) MI and (c) CP vary significantly according to "gender" variable.

H5: (a) OBSE, (b) MI and (c) CP vary significantly according to "marital status" variable.

H6: (a) OBSE, (b) MI and (c) CP vary significantly according to "age" variable.

H7: (a) OBSE, (b) MI and (c) CP vary significantly according to "income status" variable.

H8: (a) OBSE, (b) MI and (c) CP vary significantly according to "working time in the tourism sector" variable.

H9: (a) OBSE, (b) MI and (c) CP vary significantly according to "working time in the enterprise" variable,

Figure 1: conceptual model of the research.

Source: own elaboration.

3 METHODOLOGY

In this research, it is aimed to investigate the effect of employees' organization-based self-esteem on the moonlighting intention and contextual performance in tourism enterprises. Within the framework of this purpose, 397 respondents employed in tourism enterprises in different provinces of Turkey were reached by using the simple random sampling method. Data was collected between June to September 2021. Respondents were reached through a questionnaire. The sample of the research is the employees who work in the tourism industry in Türkiye, which was randomly determined to represent the universe.

The study was conducted in quantitative research design. In a quantitative study, the effects on the dependent variables are assessed using the independent variables (Thomas et al., 2015). In the study, moonlighting intention and contextual performance were used as dependent variables and organization-based self-esteem is used as an independent variable.

The survey form of the research consists of four sections. The first part consists of questions such as gender, marital status, age, income status, working time in the tourism sector and working time in the enterprise to determine the demographic characteristics of the participants. In the second section of the questionnaire, the Moonlighting Intention Scale, developed by Seema and Sachdeva (2020) and adopted into a 7-item scale with one additional item by Seema et al. (2021) was used to determine the moonlighting intention of the participants.

A 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1= strongly disagree to 5= strongly agree) was used. Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the scale was determined as α 0.747 in the study. In the third part of the questionnaire, the OBSE scale consisting of 10 items developed by Pierce et al. (1989) was

used to determine the OBSE level of the employees. Cronbach's alpha coefficient α of the scale was determined as 0.897. In the fourth part of the questionnaire, the Contextual Performance Scale, in which the "personal industry" and "loyal boosterism" dimensions of the organizational citizenship behavior scale developed by Moorman and Blakely (1995) and refined by Jawahar and Carr (2007) was used to determine the contextual performance level of the participants. In this study, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the scale was determined as α 0.860.

In the research, the data obtained through the questionnaire method were analyzed through the statistical software. Correlation analysis to determine the relationship between OBSE practices, employees' moonlighting intention and contextual performance in tourism enterprises; and regression analysis to determine the effect of OBSE on moonlighting intention and contextual performance was conducted. Independent sample t test and ANOVA were carried out to determine significance of the differences between variables such as OBSE, MI and CP according to demographic characteristics.

Table 1. Proportional and numerical distribution of the sample profile.

Variables		f	%
Gender	Male	212	53,40
	Female	185	46,60
Marital Status	Married	173	43,60
	Single	224	56,40
Age Group	20 and below	15	3,80
	21-30	145	36,50
	31-40	127	32,00
	41-50	88	22,20
	51 and above	22	5,50
Monthly Income	2.825 TL and below	78	19,60
	2.826 TL - 5.650 TL	189	47,60
	5.650 TL - 8.475 TL	104	26,20
	8.476 TL and above	26	6,50
Working Time in Tourism Sector	Less than 1 year	45	11,30
	1-5 years	101	25,40
	6-10 years	81	20,40
	11-15 years	56	14,10
	More than 16 years	114	28,70
Working Time in Enterprise	Less than 1 year	72	18,10
	1-5 years	167	42,10
	6-10 years	78	19,60
	11-15 years	42	10,60
	More than 16 years	38	9,60
TOTAL		397	100,00

Source: own elaboration.

As it is shown in the Table 1, 53.4% of the employees are male and 46.6% are female. Considering their marital status, 43.6% of the employees are married and 56.4% are single participants. In the age distribution, the largest proportion of respondents 145 (36.5%) were in the 21 - 30 age range while the respondents aged 20 and below 15 (%3,8) represented the lowest proportion. Highest percentage of respondents were in between 2,826 TL - 5,650 TL monthly income range (47.6%), and the lowest proportion of them were with a monthly income 8,476 TL and above (6,5%).

Among the employees, who have worked in the tourism sector, 1-5 years (25.4%) constituted the highest

proportion while 45 (11.3%) of respondents who have worked in the tourism sector for less than 1 year were in the lowest segment. The majority of the employees 167 (42.10%) responded that, they have worked in the same business for 1-5 years. That was followed by 19.6% for 6-10 years, 18.1% for less than 1 year, 10.6% for 11-15 years and 9.6% for 16 years or more.

4 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The hypotheses of the research were tested by applying correlation, regression, t-test and ANOVA analysis to the data obtained from the questionnaires applied to the sample group.

Table 2. The relationship between organization-based self-esteem, moonlighting intention and contextual performance.

	Moonlighting Intention	Contextual Performance
Organization-Based Self-Esteem	Pearson Correlation -,206**	,912**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0,000
	N	397

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: own elaboration.

As indicated in Table 2 above, there is a very weak and negative relationship between employees' OBSE and moonlighting intention ($r = -.206$). According to this result, it can be concluded that, as the level of OBSE increases, the moonlighting intentions of the employees decrease.

Moreover, it can be reported that, there is a very high level of positive correlation between employees' OBSE and the contextual performance ($r = .912$). According to this result, it was observed that the contextual performance of the employees increased as the level of OBSE increased. In this context, these relationships support the hypothesis H1 with sufficient evidence that there is a significant relationship between OBSE, moonlighting intention and contextual performance.

Table 3. Regression analysis demonstrating the effect of organization-based self-esteem on moonlighting intention and contextual performance.

	DEPENDENT VARIABLES			
	Moonlighting Intention		Contextual Performance	
R ²	0,042		0,831	
Independent Variable	B	p	B	p
Organization-Based Self-Esteem	0,309	0,000	0,912	0,000

Source: own elaboration.

According to the results of the regression analysis performed in Table 3, 4% of moonlighting intention ($R^2=0.034$) and 83% of contextual performance ($R^2=0.831$) could be explained by OBSE according to the R^2 coefficient of determination value. However, when the significance (p) values are examined; all relationships between dependent and independent variables are significant.

According to these findings, a one-unit increase in OBSE leads to a -0.309 unit decrease in the moonlighting intention of the employees, who constitute a sample of, provides a 0.930 increase on the contextual performance. These results support the hypotheses that "H2: OBSE has a significant effect on moonlighting intention" and H3: "OBSE has a significant effect on contextual performance" with sufficient evidence.

According to these findings, the fact that employees are valued, trusted and taken seriously by others in the business they work, will enable these employees to take care not to be disruptive in their work even if they have a valid excuse, to defend the business in against criticism and to be proud of it. Otherwise, employees may frequently consider having a second job outside of their primary occupation, and if offered, they may be more likely to accept another job in addition to their current job.

It is possible to say that this circumstance may cause the employee to direct his/her energy and performance to the second job. In addition, according to Costa et al., (2022), some employees may be ineffective in making use of their free time, as they are conditioned to certain obstacles that prevent them using their time more effectively. These restraints, which primarily affects women, causes physical and mental exhaustion, making it difficult to concentrate on anything but rest.

Table 4. Differences between gender of participants and organizational-based self-esteem, moonlighting intention and contextual performance.

	Variables	f	Mean	S.D.	F	p
OBSE	Male	212	4,05	0,85	0,100	0,515
	Female	185	4,00	0,84		
MI	Male	212	2,44	1,30	0,245	0,571
	Female	185	2,37	1,26		
CP	Male	212	4,04	0,86	0,147	0,617
	Female	185	3,99	0,88		

Source: own elaboration.

No significant differences were found between gender and OBSE, moonlighting intention, and contextual performance ($p>0.05$). In this context, OBSE, moonlighting intention, and contextual performance do not vary by gender (Table 4). So the hypotheses, (a) OBSE, (b) MI and (c) CP differ according to H4 gender variable are not supported by sufficient evidence.

Table 5. Differences between marital status of participants and organization-based self-esteem, moonlighting intention and contextual performance.

	Variables	f	Mean	S.D	F	p
OBSE	Married	173	4,08	0,86	0,0	0,247
	Single	224	3,98	0,84		
MI	Married	173	2,15	1,26	0,2	0,000*
	Single	224	2,61	1,26		
CP	Married	173	4,08	0,84	0,8	0,171
	Single	224	3,96	0,88		

* $p<0,05$

Source: own elaboration.

No significant difference was found between the marital status of the participants and their OBSE and

contextual performance ($p>0,05$). Within this framework, OBSE and contextual performance do not vary based on the marital status (Table 5). However, according to Table 5, a significant difference was determined between participants' marital status and their moonlighting intention ($p<0.05$). In this context, moonlighting intention shows a difference according to the marital status of the employees.

Accordingly, hypotheses "(a) OBSE and (c) CP differ according to the H5 marital status variable" are not supported by sufficient evidence, while the hypothesis "(b) AN differs according to the marital status variable" is supported with sufficient evidence. However, it is among the results of this study that married employees have less moonlighting intentions than single employees.

Table 6. Differences between age groups of participants and organization-based self-esteem, moonlighting intention and contextual performance.

	Variables	f	Mean	S.D.	F	p
OBSE	20 and below	15	3,86	1,17	0,199	0,939
	21-30	145	4,01	0,80		
	31-40	127	4,04	0,84		
	41-50	88	4,04	0,86		
	51 and above	22	4,09	1,00		
MI	20 and below	15	3,42	1,37	18,290	0,000*
	21-30	145	2,73	1,23		
	31-40	127	2,61	1,23		
	41-50	88	1,61	0,99		
	51 and above	22	1,68	1,16		
CP	20 and below	15	3,89	1,29	0,308	0,873
	21-30	145	3,98	0,86		
	31-40	127	4,03	0,85		
	41-50	88	4,05	0,79		
	51 and above	22	4,14	1,00		

* $p<0,05$

Source: own elaboration.

No significant difference was found between the age group of the participants and their OBSE and contextual performance ($p>0.05$). These results reveal that OBSE and contextual performance do not differ significantly across age groups (Table 6). According to Table 6, significant differences was found between the age group of the participants and their moonlighting intention ($p<0.05$). In other words, moonlighting intention shows a difference according to the age of the employees.

Therefore, hypotheses (a) OBSE and (c) CP differ according to the H6 age variable are not supported with sufficient evidence, while the hypothesis (b) "MI differs according to the H6 age variable" is supported with sufficient evidence. However, when mean scores of age groups were considered, employees aged 41-50 exhibit less moonlighting than employees aged 20 and under.

No significant difference was found between the monthly income of the participants and their OBSE and contextual performance ($p>0.05$). These results reveal that OBSE and contextual performance do not differ according to monthly income (Table 7). However, according to Table 7, significant differences was found between the monthly income of the participants and their moonlighting intention ($p<0.05$).

Table 7. Differences between monthly income of participants and organizational-based self-esteem, moonlighting intention and contextual performance.

	Variables	f	Mean	S.D.	F	p
OBSE	2.825 TL and below	78	4,02	0,90	0,943	0,420
	2.826 TL - 5.650 TL	189	3,97	0,77		
	5.650 TL - 8.475 TL	104	4,10	0,89		
	8.476 TL and above	26	4,21	1,05		
MI	2.825 TL and below	78	3,12	1,23	15,134	0,000*
	2.826 TL - 5.650 TL	189	2,44	1,28		
	5.650 TL - 8.475 TL	104	1,93	1,11		
	8.476 TL and above	26	1,99	1,11		
CP	2.825 TL and below	78	4,09	0,92	1,923	0,125
	2.826 TL - 5.650 TL	189	3,91	0,77		
	5.650 TL - 8.475 TL	104	4,11	0,93		
	8.476 TL and above	26	4,21	1,08		

* p<0,05

Source: own elaboration.

Owing to this result, moonlighting intention shows a difference according to the monthly income of the employees. As a consequence, hypotheses "(a) OBSE and (c) CP differ according to the H7 monthly income variable" are not supported with sufficient evidence, while the hypothesis (b) "MI differs according to the H7 monthly income variable" is supported with sufficient evidence.

Table 8. Differences between working time of the participants in the tourism sector and organizational-based self-esteem, moonlighting intention and contextual performance.

	Variables	f	Mean	S.D.	F	p
OBSE	Less than 1 year	45	4,08	0,75	3,525	0,008*
	1-5 years	101	4,07	0,84		
	6-10 years	81	3,72	0,98		
	11-15 years	56	4,19	0,79		
	More than 16 years	114	4,11	0,78		
MI	Less than 1 year	45	3,31	1,04	24,626	0,000*
	1-5 years	101	2,68	1,24		
	6-10 years	81	2,85	1,29		
	11-15 years	56	2,11	1,06		
	More than 16 years	114	1,65	1,04		
CP	Less than 1 year	45	4,17	0,84	4,387	0,002*
	1-5 years	101	4,02	0,85		
	6-10 years	81	3,68	0,99		
	11-15 years	56	4,16	0,80		
	More than 16 years	114	4,12	0,77		

* p<0,05

Source: own elaboration.

A significant difference was determined between the participants' working time in the tourism sector and OBSE, moonlighting intention and contextual performance (p<0.05). This result indicates that, OBSE, moonlighting intention, and contextual performance differ according to the working time of the employees in the tourism sector (Table 8). Correspondingly, the hypotheses H8: "(a) OBSE, (b) MI and (c) CP differ according to the working time in the tourism sector" are supported by sufficient evidence.

However, when the mean scores are examined, the employees who have worked in the tourism sector for 6-10 years agree less with the statements on the OBSE scale than

the employees who have worked for 11-15 years, while those who have worked for 16 years or more have less moonlighting intention. It is also observed that, employees who have worked for 6-10 years in the tourism sector have lower contextual performance than those who have worked between 11-15 years.

Table 9. Differences between working time of the participants in the enterprise and organizational-based self-esteem, moonlighting intention and contextual performance

	Variables	f	Mean	S.D.	F	p
OBSE	Less than 1 year	72	4,07	0,76	3,167	0,014*
	1-5 years	167	3,87	0,91		
	6-10 years	78	4,23	0,86		
	11-15 years	42	4,22	0,39		
	More than 16 years	38	3,98	0,96		
MI	Less than 1 year	72	3,11	1,09	24,879	0,000*
	1-5 years	167	2,72	1,21		
	6-10 years	78	2,04	1,26		
	11-15 years	42	1,32	0,78		
	More than 16 years	38	1,68	1,09		
CP	Less than 1 year	72	4,04	0,83	2,135	0,076
	1-5 years	167	3,88	0,95		
	6-10 years	78	4,12	0,86		
	11-15 years	42	4,24	0,40		
	More than 16 years	38	4,09	0,88		

* p<0,05

Source: own elaboration.

A significant difference was determined between the participants' working time in the enterprise and OBSE, moonlighting intention and contextual performance (p<0.05). This result indicates that, OBSE, moonlighting intention and contextual performance differ according to the working time of the employees in the tourism sector. However, there was no significant difference between the working time of the participants in the enterprise and the contextual performance (p>0.05).

Thus, contextual performance does not differ according to working time in the enterprise (Table 9). As a consequence, the hypotheses H9: "(a) OBSE and (b) MI differs according to the variable of working time in the enterprise" are supported by sufficient evidence, while the hypothesis "(c) CP differs according to the variable of working time in the enterprise" is not supported with sufficient evidence

5 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In this study, which aims to investigate the effects of organization-based self-esteem on moonlighting intention and contextual performance in the tourism industry, it is inferred that employees who cannot participate in the organization or who have difficulties in participation may feel isolated in the organization they belong to, and therefore might not be able to reveal their contextual performance.

On such occasions, it becomes intrinsically inevitable for the employees who are not satisfied with the organizational environment and what the organization brings to them, to seek another work or organizational environment.

Subsequently, moonlighting intention emerges at the point where the employee feels the uncertainty about the future.

Only a few previous studies exist that investigate Moonlighting Intention, OBSE, and Contextual Performance variables in the same plot, specifically in the hospitality and tourism context. However, no studies have examined these variables simultaneously. The current study fills the gap in the existing literature by examining these variables together.

According to the results of the correlation analysis conducted in this study, which aims to determine the effect of OBSE on moonlighting intention and contextual performance in tourism enterprises and to examine the differentiation of research variables in terms of demographic factors, there is a negative very weak relationship between OBSE and employees' moonlighting intention. In addition to this result, a positive relationship between OBSE and contextual performance was determined.

It was also observed that as the level of OBSE increases, the moonlighting intentions of the employees decreases and the contextual performance of the employees increases. From this perspective, the H1 hypothesis is supported by sufficient evidence. According to the results of the regression analysis conducted in the research, employees' moonlighting intention and contextual performance could be explained by the OBSE and all the relationships between the variables were statistically significant.

In addition, it was determined that a one-unit increase in employees' OBSE resulted in a decrease in the moonlighting intention of the employees and an increase in their contextual performance. In this context, these findings support the H2 and H3 hypotheses with sufficient evidence.

According to the differentiation analyzes conducted in the research, no significant difference was found between the gender, marital status, age, income status and OBSE level of the participants. Therefore, hypotheses H4a, H5a, H6a, H7a were not supported with sufficient evidence, while hypotheses H8a and H9a were supported with sufficient evidence.

No significant difference was found between the gender of the participants and their moonlighting intention, but a significant difference was found between marital status, age, income status, working time in the tourism sector, working time in the enterprise and moonlighting intention. In this context, while the H4b hypothesis is not supported by sufficient evidence, the H5b, H6b, H7b, H8b and H9b hypotheses are supported by sufficient evidence.

No significant difference was found between the gender, marital status, age, income status, working time in the enterprise and contextual performance of the participants, but a significant difference was found between the working time in the tourism sector and the contextual performance. Accordingly, the H4c, H5c, H6c, H7c and H9c hypotheses are not supported by sufficient evidence, whereas the H8c hypothesis is supported by sufficient evidence.

In conclusion, considering the negative effects of OBSE on moonlighting intention and positive effects on contextual performance in tourism enterprises, organizations need to recognize OBSE. Based on the results of this research and the information in the literature, the following suggestions can be concluded.

The fact that employees are taken seriously as a respected person in the business they are employed, valued and believed in, and that these employees are productive and able to make a difference in the business will reduce the idea of having a second job outside the business and increase their performance by enabling them to spend their effort and energy on their primary job.

Otherwise, employees will waste their time and energy working in a second job, think about getting a second job, or keep up with job postings. This circumstance may adversely affect the productivity, competitiveness and continuity of the enterprise. However, a positive level of OBSE in the business will enable employees to suggest new ways to achieve goals or objectives, to come up with new and practical ideas to boost business performance, to suggest new ways to enhance the quality, to exhibit their creativity in their work and to develop new methods in the workplace.

In this regard, the employee will be able to feel committed to the organization and will not avoid taking on extra duties and responsibilities beyond his/her job requirements. Overall, these findings are in accordance with findings reported by Fan et al. (2014) concludes that, impacts that improve well-being and relieve burnout are more potent in employees with high OBSE.

Additionally, a study conducted by Lin et al. (2018) on restaurant employees reveals that employees with low OBSE frequently avoid taking part out of a fear of failing, skipping out on possibilities for accomplishment, and thus crumbling their sense of self-worth. Additionally, positive effects on OBSE and motivation level are observed in employees with strong achievement-striving traits.

It is noteworthy that among previous studies, Hur et al. (2021) reported that, the OBSE of frontline employees is improved by higher recognition and self-worth and that, creating a culture that supports safety across the entire organization is more likely to be directly connected with OBSE than other extra-role safety practices.

Furthermore, a recent study by Dalgıç & Akgündüz (2022) also concluded that, in hotels, OBSE and social exchange could strengthen job dedication and thus lower their turnover intentions. However, depending on the OBSE, employees' contextual performance and their willingness to develop new and creative ideas that have positive contributions to the image of the enterprise could reduce the risks of making wrong decisions in the business.

In tourism enterprises, employees should be made to feel that they are important to the organization. Therefore, employees will be able to perform more effectively in order for the organization to be successful and will be able to provide customer satisfaction by reflecting this to the customers. At this point, in hospitality industry, HR department plays a critical role in handling issues related to promotions, discussion of attrition, pay incentives, turnover intention, evaluations and rewards by virtue of effective communication, job rotations and entertaining periodic leaves (Kumar, 2021).

In another study, Yang et al., (2020) found a positive relationship between proactive personality traits of frontline employees and contextual performance. Moreover, Ma et al., (2021) suggested that an effective empowerment strategy can have vital effects on the way of gaining self-esteem to

hotel employees and that empowerment can also support employees' contextual performance.

This study has limitations in some aspects. In the research, the employees who work in tourism enterprises in Türkiye, including food and beverage facilities, hotels, travel agencies, and transportation services were determined as the study extent. Future researchers can conduct more in-depth research in various areas for broad-ranging findings. For further researchers, a new six-item self-report measure OB-GSE (Organization Based General Self Esteem) introduced by Filosa & Alessandri (2022) can also be a constructive and updated scale that consists of a four-sample data pattern.

Trusting in the employees in tourism enterprises will help the organization to benefit from the talent and creativity of the employees at the highest level, improve the efficiency of the organization and help organizations to make the most effective use of human resources. Thus, the decrease in the employee turnover rate will accelerate and, in the organization, the time and resources to be allocated for in-service training will be saved. Besides, the research of new technologies, processes, techniques or product ideas within the scope of the profession would increase the ability of the organization to adapt to environmental variables, and this will help to establish effective coordination methods among members of the organization.

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CRedit author statement

Term	Definition	Author	Author 2
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	X	
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	X	
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	x	
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs		x
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	X	
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	X	
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	X	
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	X	
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)		X
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or postpublication stages		X
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation		x
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	X	
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution	x	
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication		x

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